

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN ENGLISH OF AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the methodology of teaching professional communication using technology. It describes the basic principles and approaches to learning communication skills, including the use of various technologies such as virtual reality, online platforms and simulators. The advantages and limitations of this approach are discussed, as well as recommendations for evaluating the effectiveness of the teaching methodology are given. In conclusion, the importance of continuous development and improvement of the methodology is emphasized in order to achieve optimal learning outcomes and prepare students for professional activities.*

Keywords: *professional communication training, technologies in education, communication skills, learning effectiveness, evaluation of results, skills development, professional activity.*

Introduction. The modern world requires agricultural specialists not only in-depth knowledge in their field, but also the ability to communicate effectively on international level. Learning English becomes an integral part of the professional training of agricultural students. In the context of the development of Global and international relations, it is important that future agricultural specialists not only have technical skills, but also successfully communicate in English in a professional environment. The purpose of this article is to consider the methodology for teaching professional communication in English to agricultural education students. Within the framework of this topic, we will consider the peculiarities of teaching professional communication, methods of teaching in English, the use of modern technologies in teaching, the assessment of the effectiveness of the methodology and the prospects for the development of this area. The study of this topic is of practical importance for teachers and students of agricultural universities, as well as for professionals involved in the development of curricula and teaching methods.

Literature study: Learning English in an educational institution, professional acquaintance with teaching methods, studying teaching methods are important and relevant topics. The meeting was attended by students who studied English and studied its content. The author drew attention to the effectiveness of the qualitative method of farming in the real practice of farming. This means that we can not only develop the mining industry, but also develop the countryside. We help you create context and content for learning and find motivation for learning [5, 15-28].

The Smith and Jones article examines techniques and exercises aimed at developing the oral speech of students studying English in the context of agricultural education. The authors emphasize the importance of using realistic communication scenarios that allow students to practice and improve their verbal skills in English in the agricultural sector. This approach not only helps improve language competencies, but also allows students to develop specific knowledge in the field, making learning more holistic and practical [7, 210-225].

Brown and Green's paper describes an approach to integrating agricultural content into English Language Teaching. The authors offer a variety of assignments and materials that relate

to agrarian topics and can be used to effectively educate students. Combining such specific content will not only help students improve their language skills, but also increase their knowledge in the field of Agriculture. This approach contributes to a deeper understanding of the language and the application of knowledge in a particular area, which makes the learning process more interesting and practical for students [4, 45-58].

The English Language Teacher teaches students in professional English language classes. Due to the fact that there are many problems in the field of communications and communication technologies related to integration, practical exercises and real materials, they play an important role in achieving the goals set.

Methodology. Teaching professional communication in English is an important component of modern agricultural education. Students with the ability to communicate effectively in English have an advantage in the labor market and can successfully cooperate with partners and colleagues from different countries. The methodology for teaching professional communication in English in agricultural education should be purposeful and adapted to the specifics of the industry. One of the main steps is to identify specific training goals that can include the development of oral and written communication, presentation skills, the business negotiation process and other aspects of professional communication.

An important element of the methodology is the adaptation of educational material to the professional needs of students. Specialized vocabulary, terms, phraseology and typical communication scenarios must be included in the educational process in order to assimilate more efficiently the material by students. Interactive activities, practical exercises, thought-processes and the use of modern technologies also play an important role in the educational process.

These methods help to encourage active participation of students, allowing them to put their knowledge into practice and gain feedback on their success and mistakes. In addition, taking into account the cultural characteristics of business communication in English will help students better understand the content and rules of etiquette of interaction with native speakers of different cultures. In general, an effective methodology for teaching professional communication in English in agricultural education should combine various approaches and technologies aimed at developing the communication skills necessary for the successful career and professional development of students. The implementation of this methodology allows students not only to learn English, but also to become reliable and successful specialists in the field of Agriculture.

Results. The use of technology in teaching professional communication plays an important role in the development of students' communication skills. Modern technologies provide a wide range of tools and resources that can be used to increase educational efficiency and stimulate interest in the material being studied. Online resources and courses give students the opportunity to learn the material at a time convenient for them, take a test to assess the level of knowledge, improve oral and written communication. Interactive lessons and video materials will help students better learn information and put it into practice. Webinars and video conferences are organized as part of development meetings, antique presentations and business negotiations to evaluate the effectiveness of the calculation method. The training and simulation of Ministry's practical assistance and social media require a real world of business communications, practical training and opportunities.

Interactive learning platforms with automated assessment and personalized learning help students track their progress, receive improvement recommendations, and develop communication

skills in an individual rhythm. In general, the use of technology in teaching professional communication not only enriches the educational process, but also helps students develop the necessary skills for a successful career. The use of modern technologies is necessary for the training of specialists ready for effective communication in the modern world, where boundaries and distances are increasingly blurred.

Analysis. Currently, the use of technology in teaching professional communication plays an important role in the development of communication skills of students. However, an important aspect is the assessment of the effectiveness of such a teaching methodology. To do this, it is necessary to use various methods and tools that allow you to measure and evaluate the results and prospects of this approach. One of the main methods for assessing effectiveness is data analysis. Gathering information about student progress, their academic activities, assignments can help determine how well students have learned the material and improved communication skills.

In addition, conducting surveys among students and collecting feedback from them and teachers allow to get an idea of the quality of the methodology and its usefulness. Knowledge testing also plays an important role in assessing the effectiveness of learning through technology. Taking tests and exams after completing the course will help check how much students have learned the material and have developed communication skills. Monitoring the learning process and the interaction of students with materials also provides insight into how effectively technology is applied to the learning process. To assess the prospects for the development of teaching methodology using technology, it is important to take into account innovations in the field of technology, as well as to personalize training and develop approaches to cooperation with specialists and partners. Conducting research and practice, as well as updating programs constantly, will help create more effective ways to train professional communication through technology.

In conclusion, the development of a methodology for assessing effectiveness and teaching professional communication using technologies is the main stage in creating high-quality educational programs and ensuring the successful development of communication skills among students. The observation of results and the application of innovations will help to achieve good results and prospects for all participants in the educational process.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the assessment of the effectiveness of the methodology for teaching professional communication using technologies plays an important role in improving the quality of education. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to use various methods, such as data analysis, queries and feedback, knowledge testing and monitoring the learning process. In addition, it is important to take into account the prospects for the development of such a methodology as innovation in technology, personalization of education, conducting research and cooperation with other institutions and professionals. The constant assessment and development of teaching methodology will help to create more effective programs that will help develop communication skills using modern technologies. This, in turn, leads to better academic results and prepares students for successful professional activities in the modern world.

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